

Interconnected DC Microgrid Control Using Switch-Mode Power Supplies Set-Ups

Pascal Hategekimana ^a, Adrià Junyent-Ferré ^b

^a *Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department, University of Rwanda, P.O. Box 3900, Kigali, Rwanda*

^b *Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department, Imperial College London, London SW7 2BX, UK*

Abstract

After more research on solar PV-based DC microgrid (DCMG) network topology, protection, and control strategies in the remote village of Rwanda, readings and simulations were not enough to complete this work, and the project implementation was carried out to validate the simulated results. The materials and steps involved are shown and discussed in this subsection. In this work, the power source was considered a buck converter to power the two electrical loads (variable resistances). The role of Switch-Mode Power Supplies (SMPS) is vital in modern power electronics as they enable efficient conversion of electrical energy across various voltage levels. However, maintaining precise control of voltage and current poses a critical challenge, particularly in applications requiring strong regulation and dynamic response. This work focuses on controlling converter output parameters using SMPS systems. The proposed approaches enhance the performance of power converters in terms of voltage regulation, efficiency, and power-sharing by incorporating methods such as droop controllers.

Keywords: droop controllers, microgrids, efficiency, voltage regulation, power-sharing

1. Introduction

Interconnected DC microgrids, which integrate multiple DC microgrids to enhance system resilience and efficiency, rely heavily on switch-mode power supplies (SMPS) for effective control and power management. SMPS are essential in these systems for voltage regulation, power sharing, and maintaining stability across interconnected microgrids. The rapid transition of renewable energy systems has positioned DCMGs as a vital solution for enhancing power system reliability, efficiency, and integration of renewable energy sources. Unlike traditional AC systems, DC microgrids offer advantages such as reduced conversion losses, simplified control mechanisms, and seamless interfacing with photovoltaic arrays, battery storage systems, and DC loads. However, the dynamic behavior and control challenges in interconnected DC microgrids necessitate robust experimental validation before deployment in real-world scenarios.

This study focuses on the hardware experimentation of interconnected DC microgrid control using SMPS setups, providing a scalable and cost-effective platform for validating various control strategies. SMPS units, with their fast dynamic response and high efficiency, are ideally suited for emulating the power electronic interfaces typically found in real microgrids. Researchers can observe and refine control

techniques under diverse operational scenarios by utilizing SMPS configurations to replicate the behavior of distributed energy resources (DERs), loads, and network interconnections. The experimental platform developed in this work allows for the implementation and evaluation of decentralized and hierarchical control schemes, load sharing, and voltage regulation strategies across interconnected microgrid segments. The interconnected topology provides a realistic environment for testing power sharing under both steady-state and transient conditions, including plug-and-play operations and fault scenarios.

The objective of this research is to demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of using SMPS-based testbeds for DC microgrid experimentation. By leveraging readily available hardware and flexible control architectures, the approach bridges the gap between theoretical control models and practical application, promoting rapid prototyping and iterative development. The results from this experimentation not only validate control strategies but also contribute to the standardization and optimization of DC microgrid technologies for future smart grid applications.

1.1. Control Strategies for Interconnected DC Microgrids

Effective control of interconnected DC microgrids is crucial for ensuring stable operation and efficient power distribution. Autonomous control strategies, such as droop control, are commonly employed to manage power sharing and voltage regulation without the need for extensive communication between microgrids. A study on autonomous control strategies for interconnected DC microgrids discusses how transactional converters can be utilized when multiple DC microgrids are connected through a common bus, highlighting the importance of autonomous control in enhancing system resilience and reliability [1]. Another approach involves consensus-based coordinated control, which enables flexible interconnection of DC microgrids through contact switches or isolated bidirectional DC-DC converters. This method allows for the flexible control of interconnected power, effectively achieving electrical isolation and improving power supply reliability [2].

1.2. Power Sharing and Voltage Regulation through SMPS

Maintaining consistent voltage levels and equitable power sharing among interconnected DC microgrids is vital. A power-sharing scheme between two interconnected ring DC microgrids, while maintaining individual bus voltages, is detailed in a study that provides insights into the mechanisms of power-sharing in such configurations [3]. Additionally, an improved droop control method has been proposed to manage power flow among interconnected microgrids by maintaining constant desired voltages, thereby enhancing voltage stability and power-sharing capabilities [4]. Switched-mode power supplies (SMPSs) are single-switch, two-state DC-DC converters classified as buck, boost, or buck-boost based on their voltage transfer functions. With over 33 types, SMPSs differ in characteristics like current and voltage ripples, stresses, and their operation as voltage- or current-sourced converters. These variations impact efficiency and application suitability, making SMPSs essential in modern power electronics. Though typically used in DC-DC mode, these SMPSs can be connected differentially to function as single- or three-phase DC-AC inverters, making them suitable for low-power applications [5]. SMPS plays a pivotal role in the operation of interconnected DC microgrids by providing efficient voltage regulation and power conversion. They are integral in implementing control strategies such as droop control and consensus-based coordination, facilitating effective power sharing and voltage stability. The design and operation of SMPS in these systems require

careful consideration of electromagnetic interference (EMI) mitigation and harmonic distortion to ensure optimal performance [6] [7].

1.3. The SMPS for Power Management in Solar PV-Based DC Microgrids

In DC microgrids, SMPS facilitates the conversion of solar energy into usable electrical power by stepping up or down voltage levels as required. This capability is crucial for integrating solar PV systems with energy storage solutions and DC loads. For instance, a study on a unified power converter for solar PV and energy storage in DC microgrids highlights the importance of SMPS in managing power flow between solar panels, batteries, and the DC grid, thereby enhancing system efficiency and reliability [8].

Effective voltage control and power management are crucial for ensuring the stability of DC microgrids. Switched-mode power supplies (SMPS) play a key role by enabling precise voltage regulation and optimizing power distribution across different components. A comprehensive review of voltage control and power management in DC microgrids highlights the role of SMPS in mitigating voltage fluctuations and enhancing power-sharing mechanisms. By addressing these challenges, SMPS contributes significantly to improving system reliability, efficiency, and overall performance in modern DC microgrid applications [9] [10] [11].

1.4. DC-DC Converters in Microgrids with SMPS

DC-DC converters, a type of SMPS, are commonly used in DC microgrids to adjust voltage levels between different components. A comprehensive overview of DC-DC converters' control methods in DC microgrids examines various topologies and control strategies, emphasizing their role in enhancing system performance and efficiency [12]. Reconfigurable solar PV systems, which adapt to changing conditions, often utilize SMPS to optimize performance. A review on reconfigurable solar PV systems explores how SMPS are applied in reconfigurable PV arrays, power conditioning units, and microgrid controllers, highlighting their flexibility and efficiency in dynamic environments [13].

1.5. Comparative Studies and Performance Analysis

Comparative studies of DC-DC converters for solar PV with microgrid applications provide insights into the performance and suitability of various converter topologies. These studies assist in selecting appropriate SMPS configurations based on factors like voltage gain, component count, and switching characteristics [14]. In this experiment, there is a need to access the following equipment: Switch-Mode Power Supplies (SMPS) as printed circuit board (PCB), variable resistors, desktop power supply unit (PSU), Digital storage oscilloscope (DSO), Digital measurement multimeter (DMM) and wires to hook it all up as shown in Figure 1. The PSU powers the SMPS-PCB and controls the loads from the variable resistors Rd1 and Rd2. Measurements can then be taken using DDM and DSO.

Figure 1: The complete experimental setup.

The experimental setup in this study uses the buck or boost converter as an integrated circuit in the SMPS. It also includes the PSU, DMM, DSO, and two electrical loads (Rd1 and Rd). The control circuit of this experiment is mainly based on the PCB of the SMPS. Here, the system can work in two modes: (i) the open-loop system (i.e. without control) and (ii) the closed-loop system as shown in Figure 4. In this study, the closed-loop control system was considered for regulating the output voltage referring to the reference values with minimum errors. The output voltage is controlled using a duty cycle from the control knob at the fixed reference voltage of 12V.

Figure 2: Experimental set-up for load voltage regulation with droop controller.

This experiment refers to Figure 2, where the output or load voltage is regulated, the load variation does not change its voltage and this voltage (8.02V) is closer to the reference voltage (V-ref) of 8.9V with a minimum voltage deviation (0.88V). Indeed, integrating SMPS into interconnected DCMGs is essential for achieving efficient power management, voltage regulation, and system stability. Research continues to refine control strategies and SMPS technologies, enhancing the performance and resilience of interconnected DC microgrid systems.

2. Methods for DCMG Control using switch-mode power supplies

Several topologies are commonly used to implement SMPS, but for this case, the hardware for the printed circuit board (PCB) of the SMPS setup is shown in Figure 3. While any topology can work for any specification, each has unique features that suit it best for a certain application. To select the best topology

for a given specification, it is essential to understand the basic operation, advantages, drawbacks, complexity, and the area of usage of a particular topology [15]. In the study of this SMPS set-up, there are four (4) switches across the top of the PCB which control the following (from left to right): (i) the low side MOSFET gate enable, (ii) the high side MOSFET gate enable, (iii) closed-loop or open-loop control modes, lastly (iv) Buck or Boost circuit mode.

Figure 3: The hardware for the printed circuit board (PCB) of SMPS for controlling the output voltage compared to the reference voltage from the converter.

Figure 4: The control circuit of this experiment is mainly based on the PCB of SMPS. Here, the system can work in two modes: (i) open-loop system and (ii) closed-loop system.

The first two switches in Figure 3 allow deciding which MOSFET is a functional switch, and which acts as a diode. The second switch enables closed-loop control (if suitable code is uploaded to the controller), and the final one selects whether it is in Buck or Boost mode, which largely affects some limiting functions and the port that provides power for the control circuitry. The final control is a blue rotary knob that provides an analog voltage for the controller to interpret. Depending on the control mode, this may be interpreted as a duty cycle command or an output voltage reference. The PSU should be set to the appropriate voltage and current limit whilst the output is not enabled. The two most used topologies in buck converter applications are synchronous and asynchronous (or non-synchronous) buck converters. These two topologies have their advantages and disadvantages from a performance point of view, where more details can be found in [16], and can be used for both open-loop and closed-loop control systems, shown in Figure 4.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Open-loop back SMPS controller

In open-loop buck converters, the fixed duty cycle results in output voltage dependency on input voltage and load conditions. Non-synchronous open-loop converters use a diode for freewheeling, causing higher conduction losses. Synchronous open-loop converters replace the diode with a low-resistance MOSFET, reducing losses, but are still unable to stabilize output voltage under varying conditions due to their fixed duty cycle. During the switching period, it is advised to maintain a short period at the cross-over between the devices conducting where neither device is turned ON, this is called the dead-time (T_d). This time is a crucial interval during the switching process, and more explanations about the T_d are found in [17]. In this work, Figure 5 shows two MOSFETs, the high side MOSFET (HMOS) and low-side MOSFET (LMOS), driving signals with dead-time. The dead-time causes a slight difference in the duty cycles between the two gate signals. It's advisable to keep the T_d as short as possible because the circuit's behaviour is partially uncontrollable during this time.

Figure 5: Minimum dead-time through HMOS and LMOS

The dead-time serves to prevent both the high-side and low-side MOSFETs from conducting simultaneously, which could result in a short circuit across the input voltage. This deliberate interval between transistor switching allows one transistor to turn off fully before the other turns on. Properly setting the dead-time is crucial to prevent shoot-through, excessive power loss, and potential damage to the converter. However, according to [18], an excessive dead-time can also lead to reduced efficiency due to body diode conduction in the MOSFETs, resulting in higher losses. In an open-loop configuration, the dead-time must be carefully tuned as there is no feedback to adjust it dynamically. Ensuring optimal dead-time is vital for maintaining converter efficiency and reliability.

3.1. Open-loop (non-synchronous) buck SMPS

The voltage control is simplistic and lacks feedback for an open-loop buck switched-mode power supply (SMPS) with a fixed duty cycle. The open loop buck converter can be achieved through two methods: (i) synchronous and (ii) non-synchronous. This means that the duty cycle of the switching element (MOSFET) is predetermined and remains constant during operation. However, there are limitations to this approach. Because the duty cycle is fixed, the output voltage is directly affected by fluctuations in the V_{in} and changes

in the load. If the input voltage fluctuates as shown in Figure 6 (or the load changes), the output voltage will deviate from the desired level, resulting in poor voltage regulation.

Figure 6: Open-loop buck SMPS with a fixed duty cycle to compare input and output voltage in non-synchronous mode.

Therefore, open-loop control is best suited for applications where the V_s is stable, and the load remains relatively constant. While the simplicity of the open-loop design offers advantages such as reduced complexity and cost, it comes at the expense of accuracy and robustness, making this approach less desirable for applications requiring precise voltage regulation. In this experiment, the V_{in} was set to 15V, while the duty cycle was 33%, leading to the average V_o of 5V. It was found that there is no change in V_{in} , and this method is known as buck non-synchronous mode. In the open-loop model, maintaining a constant V_o from the varying V_{in} is impossible. In a closed-loop system, maintaining a constant V_o is applied with various values of V_{in} . The value of the buck converter's output voltage (V_o) depends on the duty cycle (d) and V_{in} . The V_o can be determined using eq (1), while the converter efficiency (η_c) can be determined using eq (2). In the closed-loop system, it is possible to get the output voltage extremely close to the desired V_o referring to the V_{in} .

$$V_o = d \cdot V_{in} \tag{1}$$

$$\eta_c = \frac{P_o}{P_{in}} \tag{2}$$

To compare the network parameters, Figure 7 shows the converter efficiency (η_c) with varying V_{in} in the open-loop non-synchronous configurations at a fixed duty cycle. In this case, with the increase in the load current (I_o), the η_c increases to some extent due to the increase in the conduction dissipation of the components. At low I_o the η_c is generally lower due to the fixed losses, such as gate drive and switching losses of power MOSFET. At a certain time with a sufficient load current, the efficiency can start decreasing as depicted in Figure 7 by observing the time for maximum efficiency.

Open loop (non-synchronous) buck converter with constant input voltage ($V_s=15.03V$)

Figure 7: Input-output voltages and efficiency vs output current with an open-loop buck converter with fixed duty cycle and varying voltage source.

However, as I_o increases, efficiency improves because conduction losses in the MOSFET (which replaces the diode) are lower linked with the diode's forward voltage drop in a non-synchronous converter. This results in less power loss at higher currents but with certain limited value of I_o (here is at 88.6% of efficiency) referring to Figure 7. At very high I_o , the efficiency starts decreasing slightly due to increased conduction losses in the MOSFETs, but the overall efficiency remains higher. This makes synchronous buck converters particularly suitable for applications requiring high efficiency over a broad range of the V_{in} .

3.2. Open-loop synchronous buck SMPS

For further analysis, a synchronous buck SMPS is utilized to improve the negative effects of buck non-synchronous mode. This is achieved by replacing the diode with a second MOSFET, known as a synchronous rectifier, and the comparison between input and output voltage is depicted in Figure 8. When the main switch is off, this MOSFET conducts, eliminating the voltage drop associated with the diode. Consequently, the synchronous design significantly enhances efficiency, especially in low-output voltage and high-current situations. However, synchronous designs are more intricate, requiring precise switching

timing to prevent shoot-through (when both MOSFETs conduct simultaneously) and a minimum dead-time is required as previously discussed in Figure 5.

Figure 8: Open-loop buck SMPS with a fixed duty cycle to compare input and output voltage in synchronous mode

The synchronous converter achieves higher efficiency due to the MOSFET replacing the diode, leading to a significant reduction in conduction losses. This results in sustained efficiency, particularly at high currents and reduced resistive loads, due to the MOSFET's low on-resistance, which minimizes power loss. Figure 9 compares the power losses in the synchronous and non-synchronous, open-loop buck converters. In this work, the power losses increase proportionally for synchronous and non-synchronous open-loop buck converters.

Figure 9: Comparing power losses in the synchronous and non-synchronous, open-loop buck converters

In an open-loop non-synchronous buck converter, the output voltage increases linearly with the duty cycle but may decrease under heavy load conditions due to losses in the diode and other components as shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

Figure 10: Duty cycle versus output voltage in the open-loop non-synchronous buck converter

Figure 11: Duty cycle versus output voltage in the open-loop synchronous buck converter

3.3. Closed-loop buck SMPS

Closed-loop buck converters adjust the duty cycle using feedback control to maintain a stable output voltage despite input or load changes [19]. Non-synchronous converters face higher conduction losses, while synchronous ones reduce losses and provide precise voltage regulation, making them ideal for high-efficiency applications [20]. Here, with fixed source voltage and varying load resistance, efficiency is typically increased with the increase in output current, as shown in Figure 12. At low output currents (high load resistance), efficiency is lower due to the dominance of fixed losses like switching and gate drive. As output current increases (decrease in load resistance), efficiency improves, peaking at moderate to high currents where the converter operates more optimally. At very high currents, efficiency may slightly decline due to increased conduction losses in the MOSFETs, as shown in Figure 13. The closed-loop control helps maintain high efficiency by adjusting the duty cycle to optimise performance across varying loads.

Figure 12: Output voltages and efficiency versus output current with a closed-loop buck converter with a fixed voltage source and varying load resistance at low output current.

Referring to Figure 13, it can be observed that with the decrease in load resistance, there is an increase in the output current with a decrease in output voltage, and this is also associated with an increase in power losses. The closed-loop control mechanism maintains a stable output voltage, even with varying load resistance. The feedback loop adjusts the duty cycle at high currents to keep the output voltage constant. This dynamic adjustment prevents voltage sag under heavy loads. The closed-loop system continuously monitors and corrects the duty cycle, ensuring the output voltage stays within the target range despite load resistance fluctuations.

Comparing the system efficiencies for both open-loop and closed-loop buck converters, closed-loop buck controls are more efficient than open-loop because they actively regulate the duty cycle to maintain a stable output voltage, even when input voltage or load conditions change. This dynamic adjustment allows the converter to respond to changes in real-time, optimising its performance under a wide range of operating conditions. By continuously fine-tuning the duty cycle, closed-loop converters minimise the losses associated with non-ideal conditions, such as varying loads or input fluctuations, which can lead to inefficiencies in open-loop systems.

Figure 13: Output voltages and efficiency versus output current with a closed-loop buck converter with a fixed voltage source and varying load resistance at high output current.

Figure 14: Compare the efficiencies of open and Closed-loop buck converters with a fixed voltage source and varying load resistance

Open-loop buck converters have a fixed duty cycle and struggle to adapt to input voltage or load changes, leading to efficiency issues. In contrast, closed-loop control systems keep the converter operating close to its optimal point of system efficiency, improving overall energy efficiency, reliability, and power supply performance. Closed-loop buck converters are the preferred choice for consistent and efficient voltage regulation. In a closed-loop buck converter, the duty cycle adjusts to maintain a stable output voltage despite varying input voltages as depicted in Figure 15. When the input voltage is low, the duty cycle increases to compensate for and maintain the desired output voltage. This means the switch stays on longer during each cycle. Conversely, when the input voltage is high, the duty cycle decreases, meaning the switch stays on for a shorter duration to prevent the output voltage from exceeding the set level.

Figure 15: Duty cycles and output voltage under different converter input voltages: (a) $V_s=12V$ and (b) $V_s=15V$ in the closed-loop buck converter.

The closed-loop system ensures consistent output voltage by dynamically adjusting the duty cycle based on input voltage changes, and the feedback control system continuously monitors the output voltage and modifies the duty cycle to match the desired set point. For different voltage sources, shown in Figure 15 where (a) V_s is 12V and (b) V_s is 15V, in all conditions, the duty cycle managed to ensure the desired output voltages according to the change in loads. In this work, another important aspect is that the fluctuation in the V_s does not affect the output voltage (V_{ou}), and this V_{ou} is quickly restored in the rated values, as shown in both cases of fluctuation of Figure 16. The primary focus here is on how the V_{ou} can respond to fluctuations in the V_s . Without a feedback mechanism, any changes in the input voltage directly affect the output voltage, leading to potential deviations from the desired output voltage.

Figure 16: Comparing output and input voltage using the (a) open-loop and (b) closed-loop control systems.

Open-loop control: In both synchronous and non-synchronous open-loop buck converters, droop is a natural outcome due to the lack of feedback control and the internal resistive components. The non-synchronous design suffers more due to the diode's losses. Closed-loop control: Droop control can be deliberately implemented, particularly in synchronous designs, where it is more efficient and precise. This is advantageous in applications requiring coordinated load sharing among multiple converters. Usually, open-loop controls exhibit inherent voltage droop due to fixed duty cycles and resistive losses, with non-

synchronous designs having a more pronounced droop. Closed-loop designs can implement intentional droop control for better load sharing, with synchronous converters offering better efficiency and precision compared to their non-synchronous counterparts.

3.4. Droop controllers for voltage regulation and power-sharing

In DCMG applications, droop control is the fundamental method for controlling load current sharing. The traditional DC droop controller method involves the linear reduction of the DC output voltage as the output current increases. However, this method has a couple of limitations. Firstly, in a droop-controlled DC microgrid, the output voltage of each converter may differ due to line resistance, leading to degraded output current-sharing accuracy.

Figure 17: Experimental output current regulation using droop control parameters (K1 and K2) at constant converter voltage.

Secondly, the DC-bus voltage deviation increases with the load due to the droop action. The data gathered from the experiment with two cases, i.e. the droop control (K1 and K2) with two different voltage sources, were analyzed. Refer to Figure 17, the control loops are implemented locally, and the required voltage and current data are sent to the control system of the other converters through the PCB of the SMPS with possible control devices that help to achieve the required (controlled) output voltages. It has been demonstrated that, with the integral controller, accurate current sharing can be achieved. At the same time, the average output voltage can be maintained, and each voltage is guaranteed to be within an acceptable range.

Figure 18: Droop controller with two parallel converters for output voltage regulation and power-sharing at a reference voltage of 12V.

In this study, the droop controller adjusts the output voltage based on the load current to share power between converters as depicted in Figure 18 and Figure 19. The increase in output current results in the decrease of the converter output voltage of each converter, enabling proportional power-sharing between the converters for different reference voltages V_{ref} . This droop controller method is also realized by linearly reducing the dc V_{ou} as the output current increases.

Figure 19: Droop controller with two parallel converters for output voltage regulation and power-sharing at a reference voltage of 15V.

Both Figure 18 and Figure 19 shows how power is shared between the two converters based on their droop characteristics. This analysis helped to understand the droop control method in DCMGs with two parallel converters. The droop resistances R_{d1} and R_{d2} determine how much voltage drops in each converter as the power it supplies increases, thus balancing the load between the converters. The droop resistance R_d is the

droop coefficient, determining the rate of voltage decrease with increasing current. Thus, this R_d is essential to ensure stable and efficient operation. To ensure stable and efficient operation, it's crucial to consider the droop resistance, which is determined by the droop coefficient and indicates the rate of voltage decrease with increasing current. Furthermore, in systems with (n) parallel converters, droop control is a reliable technique for regulating the output voltage and facilitating balanced power sharing. By leveraging their droop characteristics, each converter adjusts its output in proportion to the shared load, thereby ensuring the proper distribution of power across all units.

4. Conclusion

This method effectively maintains a stable reference voltage at the output, while allowing the converters to dynamically respond to variations in load demand. Droop controller eliminates the need for complex communication between converters, making it an efficient and scalable solution for parallel operations. Ultimately, it ensures proportional power delivery, enhances system stability, and optimises the performance across multiple converters working in unison. The droop-based control approach provides scalability, modularity, and robustness to system changes such as source addition, load variation, or disconnection, which are common in practical microgrid applications. Experimental and simulation results validate that the proposed control architecture maintains voltage stability and achieves reliable power-sharing under various dynamic operating conditions. Moreover, the integration of SMPS in DC microgrids enhances power quality, reduces conversion losses, and supports rapid response to load transients. The decentralised nature of droop control aligns well with the distributed structure of microgrids, promoting autonomy and fault tolerance. To conclude, the use of SMPS with droop control presents a promising solution for the efficient and reliable operation of interconnected DC microgrids. This strategy supports the vision of future smart energy systems where flexibility, scalability, and resilience are essential attributes for sustainable energy distribution.

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